

A Kinetic Study on the Electrochemical Bromination of Fluorescein to Eosin in a Batch Reactor

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The bromination of fluorescein to eosin has been carried out in a batch reactor in NaHCO₃ medium using TSI anode, stainless steel cathode and nylon as the separator. The kinetics of the reaction have been followed by uv-visible spectra of samples withdrawn at various time intervals during the electrolysis. Probable mechanism for the bromination of fluorescein has been suggested and attempts have been made for reaction modeling.

Eosin (disodium salt of 2,4,5,7-tetrabromo-9-*o*-carboxy-phenyl-6-hydroxy-3-isoxanthone or tetrabromofluorescein) is a D and C color used in coloring drugs and cosmetics¹ and other industrial products^{2,3}.

The results of electrochemical synthesis of eosin from fluorescein, involving the study of the effect of anode material, diaphragm, anode current density and nature of the electrolyte on the yield and eosin content were discussed earlier^{4,5}. In the present paper, the results of a kinetic study on the bromination of fluorescein, carried out in a batch reactor, as followed by uv-visible spectrophotometry, are discussed. Attempts have been made at reaction modeling.

Theoretical :

During the electrolysis of fluorescein in NaHCO₃ medium in the presence of NaBr, the following reactions occur in the reactor. Bromine is generated *in situ* at the anode and reacts with fluorescein(Fluo) to yield eosin(Eos),

Probable secondary reactions are :

In bulk :

At anode :

At cathode :

The variation in the concentration of reactants and

products in the reactor is due to chemical or electrochemical reactions occurring in the reactor. The reactor can be assumed to behave as an ideal stirred tank batch reactor. Denoting the reaction rate as r_i corresponding to each reaction in the scheme, the mass balance can be written as (assuming that no secondary reaction occurs),

$$d[\text{Br}^-]/dt = -8 r_1 + 4 r_3 \quad (11)$$

$$d[\text{Br}_2]/dt = 4 r_1 - 4 r_3 \quad (12)$$

$$d[\text{Fluo}]/dt = -r_3 \quad (13)$$

$$d[\text{Eos}]/dt = r_3 \quad (14)$$

Now, pseudo-steady state theory can be applied for the generation and consumption of bromine, i.e. rate of formation of bromine is equal to its rate of disappearance. Then

$$r_1 = r_3 \quad (15)$$

$$d[\text{Br}^-]/dt = -4 r_3 = 4 d[\text{Fluo}]/dt \quad (16)$$

From the rate expressions for the reactions shown in equations (13) and (14), one can write

$$-d[\text{Fluo}]/dt = k_3[\text{Fluo}] \quad (17)$$

$$d[\text{Eos}]/dt = k_3[\text{Fluo}] \quad (18)$$

Br⁻ from the bulk is transported to the electrode surface, where it undergoes conversion to bromine and fluorescein is transported from bulk to electrode surface for the conversion to eosin.

Assuming Tafel behavior to be applicable,

$$i/nF = k_{1s} [\text{Br}_2]_s e^{bE} \quad (19)$$

From equations (3) or (16),

$$i/nF = 4 k_{1s} [\text{Fluo}]_s e^{bE} \quad (20)$$

$$i/nF = k_L \{ [\text{Fluo}]_b - [\text{Fluo}]_s \} \quad (21)$$

Eliminating $[\text{Fluo}]_s$ the surface concentration,

$$i/nF \{ 1/4 k_{1s} e^{bE} + 1/k_L \} = [\text{Fluo}] \quad (22)$$

$$i/nF = k[\text{Fluo}] \quad (23)$$

where, $1/k = 1/k_L + 1/4 k_{1s} e^{bE}$

Results and Discussion

A plot of absorbance versus wavelength recorded during the electrochemical bromination of fluorescein in a

batch reactor at different time intervals after the start of electrolysis is shown in Fig. 1 (some of the curves are not shown due to overcrowding). It can be seen that the λ_{\max} is initially around 492 nm corresponding to that of fluorescein, which finally shifts to a value close to 518 nm which

Fig. 1. Absorbance-Wavelength plots during the electrochemical bromination of fluorescein in a batch reactor during electrolysis after time (t /min): 0 (full line), 40 (---), 80 (- · -), 90 (●—●), 120 (●●—●●) and 166 (—■—).

corresponds to that of eosin. At intermediate times, fluorescein concentration is decreased and the eosin concentration is increased, than at zero time. However, intermediary bromination products, though may have been formed are not detectable in the spectra. The peak heights are decreased towards the end as compared to the initial one, as the absorptivities of eosin are much lower than that of fluorescein³.

The results of the uv-visible spectra were analyzed and a graph of the percentage of fluorescein and eosin (which decreased and increased respectively during the progress of the reaction) versus the electrolysis time was drawn. Both the plots are linear, indicating that a zero order reaction occurs. The zero order reaction rate can be attributed to the absorbed fluorescein and bromine (or bromide) reacting at the electrode surface and hence being independent of the bulk concentration of fluorescein. It has been reported that in the electrolysis of NaBr or HBr solutions, Ti/TiO₂, RuO₂ surface is a catalyst⁷. The adsorption of bromide ion at the anode, which could block surface oxidation to some extent, was suggested as a reason for the need for excess bromide and excess charge for the electrochemical conversion of fluorescein to eosin^{5,7}.

A plot of $\ln(C_0/C_t)$ versus time, where C_0 and C_t correspond to the concentrations of fluorescein (or eosin) at

zero time and after a time t of electrolysis respectively, was also drawn for both the disappearance of fluorescein and the appearance of eosin. Linear plots were seen in both the cases. The heterogeneous rate constants calculated from the slope values of these linear segments are 0.82×10^{-4} and $0.41 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ respectively. The difference in magnitudes observed between the disappearance rate of fluorescein and the production rate of eosin, could be attributed to the occurrence of several intermediate steps (probably involving the other bromination products) which are likely in the reaction. Secondary reaction involving the loss of bromine (by reactions 4-6 shown under theoretical treatment or due to evaporation) could also explain this behavior.

Experimental

The electrochemical bromination of fluorescein was carried out in a batch reactor in a 100 ml beaker under the optimized conditions as reported earlier, at which maximum yield of eosin was obtained⁵. A solution (50 ml) of the electrolyte consisting of fluorescein (1 g, $0.053 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), NaBr (2.187 g) and 10% (w/v) NaHCO₃ was employed. A current density of 5 A dm^{-2} was applied. Ti/TiO₂, RuO₂⁶ and stainless steel were used as the anode and cathode respectively, and nylon served as the separator. The progress of electrolysis was followed by paper chromatography⁵.

During electrolysis, the solution (0.5 ml) was removed at various time intervals and made upto 50 ml, after adding ammonia (0.5 ml). The above solution was diluted 100 times and used for measuring the spectra in the range of 400–600 nm. Blank solution consisted of the electrolyte solution as above, except the reactant. A Hitachi, U-3400 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement. From the spectra, the concentrations of unreacted fluorescein and tetrabromofluorescein were calculated.

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